

Review on Protective Clothing

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ABSTRACT

Protective clothing encompasses garments and fabric-based items engineered to shield the wearer from severe environmental conditions that could lead to injury or fatality. Protective clothing is produced through conventional textile technologies, including weaving, knitting, and non-woven methods, as well as advanced techniques such as 3D weaving and braiding, utilizing both natural and synthetic fibers. The extensive protection provided by personal protective clothing (PPC) significantly impairs heat dissipation through sweat evaporation. Consequently, tasks performed while wearing PPC, especially in hot conditions, impose substantial physiological strain and can quickly lead to worker fatigue. In ultraviolet radiation the protective clothing is the most effective approach for sun protection with minimal risk is likely to be a combination photo protective garments and the application of sunscreen to exposed areas of the body.

Keywords: Ultraviolet radiation, Photo-protective garment, Protective clothing, PPC.

INTRODUCTION

Protective clothing has become a significant segment within textiles categorized as technical or industrial. In numerous occupations, workers must do personal protective clothing (PPC) to mitigate exposure to physical and chemical hazards[1]. However, the necessity of wearing such protective attire in these conditions can result in excessive heat strain, as it impairs the developed. These incorporate a layer of finely dispersed worker's ability to dissipate heat effectively to the environment. To mitigate the heat load generated by impermeable protective clothing, permeable garments were designed and active carbon, either encapsulated in polyurethane foam or as discrete carbon particles, sandwiched between two textile layers. Thermal protective clothing is chiefly engineered to safeguard against thermal hazards, encompassing exposure to high-temperature radiant sources, flame impingement, hot liquids and gases, molten substances, and heated solids and surfaces. Defining the precise

nature and characteristics of these thermal hazards is challenging due to the myriads of environmental and physical factors involved.

CLASSIFICATION OF PROTECTIVE CLOTHING

Personal protective textiles can be further categorized based on their end-use functions, including thermal (cold) protection, flame resistance, chemical protection, mechanical impact resistance, radiation shielding, biological protection, electrical insulation, and visibility enhancement. The classification of personal protective textiles is intricate, as no singular classification comprehensively encapsulates all forms of protection. Definitions frequently overlap due to the diverse range of occupations and applications, resulting in varying requirements for technique and protection within the same class of protective clothing. Depending on their intended use, personal protective textiles can be categorized into industrial, agricultural, military, civilian, medical, sports, and space protective textiles.

FLAME PROTECTION

Protective clothing intended for flame protection must fulfil two critical functions: It must be flame-resistant and provide a heat barrier. The latter is particularly crucial if the wearer must remain near flames for extended periods. In fact, the risk of burns primarily affects body parts not covered by the clothing, as evidenced by statistics indicating that 75% of burn injuries occur on exposed areas. The utilization of non-toxic or minimally toxic combustibles is crucial for effective fire safety.

HEAT AND COLD PROTECTION

The most effective approach to mitigating cold exposure involves minimizing conductive heat loss. Garments engineered for thermal protection typically feature a multi-layered construction: An inner layer that resists moisture absorption, a middle insulating layer designed to trap air while allowing moisture transfer, and an outer layer that offers resistance to wind and water infiltration. In summer, it is crucial that the heat generated by our metabolic processes is promptly dissipated to the environment. Conversely, during winter, particularly in extreme cold conditions, it is essential to implement strategies to minimize the loss of body heat[1]. Heat stress, defined as the condition where the body is unable to effectively release excess heat to its surroundings, poses a significant problem, especially during physical exertion

CHEMICAL PROTECTION

The principal functions of chemical protective clothing are to shield against airborne chemicals, including toxic and noxious gases or fumes from vehicles, as well as dust and microorganisms suspended in the air. Safety masks equipped with activated carbon particles, which are capable of adsorbing atmospheric dust, are widely employed to combat air pollution. Protective clothing cannot be standardized across all chemical applications, as the chemical properties often differ significantly; thus, a specific chemical protective clothing (CPC) can safeguard only against a limited range of particular chemicals.

BIOLOGICAL PROTECTION

Most natural textile fibers, such as wool, silk, and cellulose, are susceptible to biological degradation by bacteria, dermatophytes, and other microorganisms. Fortunately, a range of chemicals and finishing techniques can safeguard both the textiles and their wearers from such biological threats. Textiles engineered for biological protection serve dual purposes: firstly, they shield the wearer from microbial attacks, including those by bacteria, yeasts, dermatophytes, and related organisms that can cause aesthetic, hygienic, or health issues; secondly, they protect the fabric itself from bio-deterioration due to Mold, mildew, rot producing fungi, and from being consumed by insects and other pests. Natural fibers contain lignin and other compounds that inherently possess antimicrobial properties[1]. Generally, textiles made from natural fibers exhibit superior antimicrobial characteristics compared to synthetic fibers, owing to the presence of substances like lignin and pectin. Chemical finishing is commonly employed to endow both natural and synthetic textiles with antimicrobial properties, achieved either through applying functional finishes to the fabric's surface or by creating fibers that are intrinsically resistant to microorganisms.

NBC PROTECTIVE CLOTHING

The Nuclear, Biological, and Chemical (NBC) permeable suit offers protection against toxic chemicals. This suit features a jacket with an integrated hood and trousers, and is designed to be worn directly over undergarments[4]. It is air-permeable, facilitating the evaporation of sweat. During World War I, protective clothing against chemical warfare agents (CWA) comprised rubber garments, which, along with gloves and boots, covered the entire body except for the areas shielded by the mask. Such clothing is typically described as impermeable,

Received: 22 September 2024

Revised: 7 October 2024

Accepted: 14 October 2024

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.13928078](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13928078)

meaning it prevents the penetration of CWA while also inhibiting the release of perspiration from the skin. As a result, prolonged wear of this type of clothing is exceedingly uncomfortable, and in hot climates, the duration for which it can be worn is significantly limited[4].

IMPERMEABLE SUIT

The impermeable NBC-protective suit was created for the German civil defense personnel within 245 NBC platoons, each consisting of 42 aides. The principal duties of these personnel included: Detecting chemical contaminants, collecting samples, marking and monitoring affected areas, decontaminating both individuals and equipment, and sanitizing crucial contaminated roadways. Natural fibers contain lignin and other compounds that inherently possess antimicrobial properties. Generally, textiles made from natural fibers exhibit superior antimicrobial characteristics compared to synthetic fibers, owing to the presence of substances like lignin and pectin. Chemical finishing is commonly employed to endow both natural and synthetic textiles with antimicrobial properties, achieved either through applying functional finishes to the fabric's surface or by creating fibers that are intrinsically resistant to microorganisms[4].

PERMEABLE SUITS

The Israelis proposed a novel approach to alleviating heat stress in chemical protective clothing. Given the threat posed by various vesicants and other chemical warfare agents that can penetrate the skin, there is a broad consensus on the need for effective protective clothing. While impermeable suits were initially believed to offer robust protection against these agents, their lack of breath-ability, combined with perspiration, creates an intolerable barrier to the body's natural cooling processes[4]. Consequently, a key requirement for an effective protective suit is its ability to facilitate adequate cooling of the body, which is essential for maintaining comfort and safety. This suit comprised two layers: the outer layer, constructed from a vi-nylon cotton blend, was treated for camouflage and waterproofing, while the inner layer was made of cotton flannel. One side of the inner layer was coated with an active charcoal powder-adhesive mixture, and the other side was treated with an oil-repellent layer. The suit underwent rigorous testing for various parameters, including liquid retention capacity, gas and liquid penetration, charcoal binding strength, and air tightness.

HEAT BALANCE WHEN WEARING A PROTECTIVE CLOTHING

Heat production is governed by metabolic activity. At rest, it corresponds to the energy required for the body's fundamental functions, such as respiration and cardiac function, which supply cells with oxygen and nutrients. During physical exertion, however, the demand for oxygen and nutrients by active muscles escalates, resulting in heightened metabolic activity. As muscles metabolize these nutrients for mechanical work, some of the energy is expended as external work, while the majority is dissipated as heat within the muscles[5]. The ratio of external work to the total energy consumed is referred to as the efficiency with which the body performs work. Convection plays a crucial role in heat loss. When air flows across the skin, it is typically cooler than the skin, resulting in heat transfer from the skin to the surrounding air. Additionally, heat transfer via electromagnetic radiation can be significant. When there is a temperature differential between the body's surface and environmental surfaces, heat is exchanged through radiation. Lastly, the body has another mechanism for heat loss: evaporation[2]. The body's capacity to sweat allows moisture on the skin to evaporate, thereby dissipating substantial amounts of heat from the body.

The body's ability to retain or dissipate heat is significantly influenced by various external factors.

TEMPERATURE

As the air temperature rises, the body's capacity for heat loss through convection, conduction, and radiation diminishes. When environmental temperatures exceed skin temperature, the body begins to absorb heat from its surroundings rather than expelling it[5].

AIR TEMPERATURE

This assesses the degree of convective heat loss, which involves the transfer of heat from the skin to the surrounding environment through the movement of air across the skin or entering the lungs, or conversely, if the ambient air temperature surpasses the skin temperature.

RADIANT TEMPERATURE

This value, which can be understood as the average temperature of all surfaces and objects in a given space, dictates the degree of radiant heat exchange between the skin and the

environment. In environments with elevated surface temperatures, such as steel mills or in direct sunlight, the radiant temperature may significantly surpass skin temperature, leading to a transfer of radiant heat from the environment to the skin[6].

AIR HUMIDITY

Air humidity, or the concentration of moisture in the ambient air, dictates whether sweat in vapor form moves from the skin to the environment or the reverse. Generally, the moisture concentration on the skin is higher than in the surrounding air, facilitating evaporate heat loss from the skin.

WIND SPEED

The intensity of air movement significantly influences both convective and evaporate heat dissipation. For both mechanisms, heat exchange intensifies with rising wind speeds. Consequently, in cooler conditions, the body undergoes accelerated cooling due to wind; conversely, in excessively hot and humid environments, the body experiences accelerated heating. Convection is crucial for heat loss. When air flows over the skin, it is typically cooler than the skin, leading to the transfer of heat from the skin to the surrounding air. Additionally, significant heat transfer can occur through electromagnetic radiation. When there is a temperature disparity between the body's surface and environmental surfaces, heat is exchanged via radiation. Lastly, the body employs another mechanism for heat loss through evaporation. The act of sweating facilitates the evaporation of moisture from the skin, thereby dissipating significant amounts of heat from the body.

CONCLUSION

Protective gear in construction is essential for keeping workers safe and healthy. This equipment protects them from various dangers, including falling objects, harmful substances, extreme temperatures, and heavy machinery.

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